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Guiding Young Minds

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In the classroom's gentle light,
A teacher stands, ready to ignite.
With patience strong and heart so kind,
She guides young minds, each one a find.

In rows they sit, their eyes so bright,
Eager to learn, to grasp the light.
But some may struggle, some may fear,
The lessons are new, not always clear.

She sees their doubts, their silent cries,
Behind each smile, were the lows and highs.
With words so soft, she gently cheers,
Wiping away the anxious tears.

For some, the numbers swirl and dance,
A tricky maze, a puzzling trance.
But with her help, they find their way,
Numbers align, and fears melt away.

Others stumble on the words they read,
Each letter was strange, a tangled thread.
With patient steps, she leads them through,
Pages unfold, the stories true.

In every heart, a dream takes flight,
A spark ignites, a shining light.
She nurtures dreams, she plants the seeds,
In every child, the future breeds.

Though days may bring both joy and strife,
She shapes young hearts; she molds their life.
With love and care, she helps them grow,
In her embrace, their talents flow.

So here's to teachers, wise and kind,
Who fills our world with hearts refined.
Their struggles are known, their efforts vast,
Guiding young minds, from first to last.

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